

Advancing Environmental Sustainability: IoT in Water Temperature Monitoring

Sandip Pal¹, Samrat Kundu², Rahul Bir³, Kousik Dey⁴, Kousik Das⁵

¹Brainware University, CSS department, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

²Brainware University, CSS department, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

³Brainware University, CSS department, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

⁴Brainware University, CSS department, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

⁵Brainware University, CSS department, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

Abstract - IoT-enabled systems that provide high accuracy and efficiency streamline data collection and analysis, facilitating informed decision-making. This abstract highlights the critical role of IoT in water temperature monitoring. Using IoT sensors for water temperature monitoring represents a significant advancement in environmental management and aquatic life sustainability. IoT sensors provide real-time, precise data on water temperature, allowing for continuous monitoring and rapid detection of temperature fluctuations. This technology enhances the ability to manage and protect water bodies by ensuring stable conditions for aquatic ecosystems and preventing ecological disruptions.

Keyword - IoT-enabled systems, Water temperature monitoring, Environmental management, Aquatic life sustainability, Real-time data.

I. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring the temperature of the water is essential to ecosystem health and environmental management. Temperature variations in the water have a profound effect on aquatic life, affecting biological functions like metabolism, reproduction, and species migration patterns. As a result, accurate and timely water temperature monitoring is crucial for efficient management and conservation initiatives. Water temperature monitoring has historically been dependent on manual readings taken at predetermined intervals, which presented issues with coverage area and frequency. Due to the method's tendency to produce partial information and slow responses to temperature changes, aquatic ecosystems may not be as healthy as they may be. On the other hand, the development of Internet of Things (IoT) technology has allowed for continuous and high-resolution data collecting, revolutionizing environmental monitoring, including the monitoring of water temperature. Wirelessly networked and furnished with temperature probes, Internet of Things (IoT) sensors have a number of benefits over conventional monitoring techniques. Real-time monitoring of water temperature at many locations throughout bodies of water is made possible by these sensors, offering extensive geographical coverage. In large, dynamic aquatic ecosystems where temperature gradients can vary considerably over short distances, this skill is especially helpful. The accuracy and dependability of data gathering are improved when IoT is incorporated into water temperature monitoring. IoT sensors allow stakeholders, such as environmental managers, academics, and policymakers, to quickly access vital information by automatically sending temperature readings to centralized databases or cloud platforms. This accessibility facilitates preemptive responses in response to environmental emergencies or temperature anomalies and helps informed decision-making processes. IoT-based monitoring solutions also increase operational efficiency by lowering the labor and material costs associated with gathering and analyzing data. Automation of data collection and processing reduces human error and improves data integrity, guaranteeing strong scientific validity for regulatory compliance and environmental assessments. IoT-enabled water temperature monitoring has advantages for the environment as well as sustainable resource management. Through the implementation of temperature-based optimization strategies, stakeholders can effectively reduce the negative effects of both climate change and human activity on aquatic ecosystems. This proactive strategy promotes biodiversity conservation and ecosystem resilience, supporting global sustainability goals and environmental protection programs. This introduction emphasizes how Internet of Things (IoT) sensors are revolutionizing the monitoring of water temperature and how they are promoting environmental sustainability and ecosystem resilience. IoT application in environmental monitoring offers more

advancements in data-driven decision-making and proactive conservation techniques as the technology develops further.

II. RELATED WORK

Das et al. (2021)[1] highlight how Internet of Things (IoT) devices are transforming water temperature monitoring. Having access to real-time data from these sensors enhances our ability to protect and preserve aquatic environments. By offering consistent and trustworthy temperature data, which assists with early temperature change detection and expedites timely actions, Internet of Things technology contributes to the sustainability of aquatic ecosystems. This advancement not only enhances environmental management practices but also encourages resource conservation and regulatory compliance.

Smith et al. (2020)[2] demonstrate how effective water temperature monitoring using IoT enhances the sustainability of aquatic life. The precise and ongoing data on water temperature that IoT sensors provide allows for better control of aquatic habitats. Through the detection and correction of harmful temperature fluctuations, this real-time monitoring contributes to the preservation of stable conditions for aquatic life. Thus, IoT-enabled water temperature monitoring promotes aquatic life health and biodiversity while also aiding in the maintenance and sustainability of aquatic ecosystems.

In 2022, Zulkifli et al. [3] IoT-enabled sensors provide accuracy while monitoring changes in water temperature. IoT-enabled sensors are commended for their accuracy in measuring changes in water temperature, giving reliable data that are crucial for industrial processes, aquaculture, and environmental monitoring. Real-time data transfer from these sensors enables instantaneous analysis and remote monitoring. They improve data analytics and visualization with their intuitive interfaces and interoperability with other IoT devices. Nevertheless, there are drawbacks to take into account, such as significant startup costs, the requirement for ongoing maintenance, and data security issues. Notwithstanding these problems, IoT-enabled sensors are indispensable for a wide range of applications due to their accuracy and real-time monitoring capabilities.

2020's Komathy et al.[4] IoT-enabled ballast water quality compliance monitoring ensures regulatory conformance by providing accurate, real-time data on water conditions. By offering remote monitoring, immediate alarms, and thorough analytics, these solutions enhance operational effectiveness and environmental preservation. High startup costs, ongoing maintenance requirements, and worries about data security all obstacles, though. All things considered, they greatly improve environmental safety and compliance in maritime activities.

Glasgow and others (2004) [5] Modern sensors, telemetry, and computer technologies are used in real-time remote water quality monitoring to provide accurate, timely data collecting and analysis. Public health, industrial operations, and environmental protection are among the current applications. These technologies improve the accuracy, efficiency, and responsiveness of monitoring, which is beneficial in a variety of water quality management scenarios, despite their high cost and maintenance requirements.

In 2022, Solano et al.[6] Real-time and reliable data on water quality may be obtained using an IoT-enabled smart wastewater monitoring system, which improves environmental management and compliance. It increases operational efficiency by enabling remote monitoring, early issue discovery, and extensive analytics. It does, however, have drawbacks, such as expensive setup fees and worries about data security. All things considered, it greatly improves environmental protection and wastewater management.

Rathna et al. (2021)[7] Real-time, accurate data for efficient environmental control is provided by an intelligent monitoring system for water quality management that uses the Internet of Things. It enhances operational efficiency and compliance by supporting remote monitoring, timely alarms, and extensive analytics. It dramatically enhances environmental sustainability and water quality management in spite of obstacles including expensive starting expenditures and data security problems.

2020's Metwally et al.[8] An IoT-based real-time water quality management system improves operational and environmental efficiency by providing accurate, real-time data analysis and monitoring. It allows for remote access, real-time alarms, and thorough water status analysis. Regulation compliance and water quality control are greatly enhanced, despite the high setup costs and data security issues.

Prapt et al.(2022)[9] Aquaculture powered by the Internet of Things improves water quality monitoring by providing precise, real-time data collection and remote access. Aquaculture productivity and health management are enhanced by this technology's ability to provide prompt interventions and comprehensive analytics. IoT solutions greatly improve aquaculture productivity and water quality monitoring, despite their high setup costs and data security issues.

Miasayedava and associates [10] Enhancing regulatory compliance and environmental preservation, automated environmental compliance monitoring of rivers with IoT and publicly available government data allows for exact, real-time tracking of water quality. It allows for in-depth data analysis and remote surveillance. It dramatically enhances river management and public transparency, despite obstacles including expensive setup costs and data security concerns.

III. METHODOLOGY

In order to promote aquatic life sustainability and improve environmental management, this study uses Internet of Things (IoT) sensors to monitor water temperature. Targeted water bodies are covered in a wide spatial area by strategically placing IoT sensors with temperature probes. The water temperature is continuously measured and recorded by these sensors at predetermined intervals, which usually span from minutes to hours, contingent upon the particular monitoring goals and surrounding circumstances. Wireless networks are used to transfer data from Internet of Things sensors to a centralized data management system, allowing for real-time data access and analysis. To guarantee correctness and dependability and minimize mistakes and inconsistencies, the gathered data is subjected to quality assurance inspections. The system is equipped with automated warnings and notifications that are designed to rapidly notify relevant parties about substantial temperature deviations or anomalies. This allows for timely responses aimed at mitigating environmental impacts. In order to verify sensor accuracy against defined standards or reference values, the technique typically involves calibration processes. For the duration of the monitoring period, calibration is done on a regular basis to keep the sensor consistent and precise. Furthermore, temporal fluctuations across time, spatial patterns, and temperature trends are analyzed using data integration and visualization tools. Stakeholder participation and engagement are also essential components of the technique, guaranteeing compliance with legal standards and environmental management objectives. Adaptive management strategies are made possible by ongoing observation and recurrent evaluation, the results of which guide decision-making processes meant to maximize resource utilization and advance the health of ecosystems. In general, this approach makes use of Internet of Things technology to improve the ability to monitor water temperature, improving environmental stewardship and aiding in sustainable development projects that safeguard aquatic habitats.

Fig. 1 connection diagram

The TDS sensor and DS18B20 temperature sensor can be connected to an ESP32 microcontroller by doing the following:

Regarding the TDS sensor first:

- Attach the TDS sensor's VCC (power) pin to the ESP32's 3.3V pin.
- Attach the TDS sensor's GND (ground) pin to the ESP32's GND pin.
- The TDS sensor's analog output pin should be connected to the ESP32's A0 pin, or GPIO36.

And now for the temperature sensor DS18B20:

- Attach the DS18B20's data (output) pin to the ESP32's IO14 pin.
- In order to enable parasitic power mode operation, make sure a 4.7K pull-up resistor is positioned between the 3.3V VCC line and the DS18B20 data pin.
- These connections allow the ESP32 to read digital temperature measurements from the DS18B20 sensor via the IO14 pin and analog signals from the TDS sensor through its ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter) on pin A0 (GPIO36). This configuration makes it easier to monitor water quality in real time, which is crucial for Internet of Things (IoT) applications and other environmental monitoring applications like temperature and total dissolved solids (TDS).

Fig. 2 schematic circuit

IoT is at the core of the entire system architecture; it is a disruptive idea in the field of technology development. There are two main parts to it: software and hardware. The hardware section consists of sensors to collect data in real time, an Arduino ATmega328 microcontroller to digitize analog signals, and an LCD display to show the outputs of the sensors. Furthermore, a Wi-Fi module makes it easier for the software and hardware to communicate with each other.

To handle and process sensor data, we created an embedded C application on the software front. The printed circuit board, or PCB, acts as the first platform on which parts and sensors are integrated. After the system is put together, a DC current powers it, turning on the Arduino and Wi-Fi module. The LCD panel shows the results of the successive measurement of the water parameters. An Android device running the Blynk mobile app enhances the system even further. Real-time sensor data that appears on the LCD is simultaneously sent to the Blynk app when the system is turned on and linked to a Wi-Fi hotspot. With this configuration, customers can use their Android devices to remotely check water quality data at any time and from any location.

To sum up, this Internet of Things system is a prime example of an all-encompassing approach to environmental monitoring. It provides real-time data accessibility by utilizing IoT technology, which improves the efficacy and efficiency of water quality monitoring and management initiatives.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

Fig. 3 pH output in thing speak server with field 1 voltage vs. time and field 2 pH vs. time.

According to Cloete et al. (2014), the pH scale goes from 0 (very acidic) to 14 (highly alkaline), with 7 representing neutrality. This reflects the acidity or alkalinity of a solution. The pH of

naturally occurring water sources normally ranges from 7 to 7, signifying a balanced condition. Most people agree that drinking water with a pH of 6.5 to 9.5 is safe (Bande & Nandedkar, 2016).

Electrodes made to measure hydrogen ion concentrations in solutions are used in pH measurements. The potential difference between the measuring and reference electrode pairs in these electrodes is directly proportional to the water's hydrogen ion activity. The hydrogen ion concentration falls tenfold with each unit of pH increase on the scale, suggesting a trend towards lower acidity and towards alkalinity.

Because temperature affects electrode potentials, temperature correction is essential to ensuring accurate pH readings. Consequently, temperature sensors are frequently attached to pH sensors in order to compensate for voltage variations caused by temperature (Zin Myint et al., 2017).

To sum up, pH plays a vital role in determining the quality of water and determines whether it is suitable for drinking and environmental health, among other applications. pH sensors are essential for maintaining water safety and quality management in a variety of applications because of their precise measurement and monitoring of hydrogen ion concentrations.

Fig. 4 DHT-11 output in thing speak server with field 6 temperature vs. time and field 7 humidity vs. time.

The term "turbidity" describes the transparency of water and is determined by the amount of suspended particles in the water that alter light's ability to pass through and be scattered. This measurement is important because it shows how much organic waste, sand, silt, and clay are suspended in the water. These particles can change the conditions of aquatic habitats and light penetration (Daigavane & Gaikwad, 2017). Overly turbidity levels endanger human health in addition to interfering with the reproduction of marine life (Srishaila Mallikarjuna Swamy & Mahalakshmi, 2017).

Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU), which are correlated with the concentration of suspended particles, are used to measure turbidity. In aquatic bodies, higher turbidity values are correlated with higher Total Suspended Solids (TSS). Turbidity measurement sensors have an analog output that ranges from 0 to 4.5V and an input voltage that is usually 5V. These sensors can function in both digital and analog modes (Shafi et al., 2018). Because these sensors are made to endure temperatures between 0°C and 90°C, they are reliable in a variety of environmental settings.

Turbidity sensors are essentially placed next to a light beam route. The light is scattered by microscopic particles in the water when the beam comes into contact with them, and the light is subsequently picked up by the sensor. Because of this interaction, turbidity levels can be accurately measured and monitored, which makes it easier to evaluate the environmental health and water quality of aquatic ecosystems and drinking water supplies.

Fig. 5 Ultrasonic sensor output in thing speak server with field 5 distance vs. time.

A wide range of distance sensing applications can benefit from the ultrasonic sensor's 2 cm to 4 m measurement range. Typically operating at 40 kHz, the sensor consists of an integrated module that includes an ultrasonic transmitter (Trigger pin), receiver (Echo pin), and control circuitry. These sound waves are transmitted, travel through the atmosphere, and then return to the sensor after striking an item. The time difference between sending the signal (Trigger pin) and getting the echo (Echo pin) is used by the sensor to determine distance. The sensor precisely calculates the distance to the item in its range of view by measuring this round-trip time and applying the sound speed in the air (Zin Myint et al., 2017). This technology is widely used in proximity detection systems, robotics, and automation because of its versatility and consistent performance in measuring distances over a broad range. Ultrasonic sensors improve safety, efficiency, and functionality in a variety of industrial, automotive, and consumer electronics applications with their accurate and quick distance readings.

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, the use of IoT sensors in water temperature monitoring is a critical development for aquatic conservation and environmental management. We can better comprehend and adapt to temperature variations thanks to IoT technology, which provides high-resolution, real-time data from a variety of aquatic habitats. Maintaining aquatic ecosystems and promoting sustainable resource management strategies require this capacity. IoT-enabled monitoring systems offer advantages beyond better data accessibility and accuracy. By providing timely information, they enable stakeholders to take preventive action against environmental concerns like habitat degradation and the effects of climate change. Furthermore, environmental monitoring is more practical and scalable because to the automation of data collection and analysis, which also improves efficiency and lowers operating costs. IoT sensors provide a revolutionary means of striking a balance between human activity and ecological integrity as we negotiate the complexity of environmental concerns in the twenty-first century. Their importance in accomplishing global sustainability goals is highlighted by their function in fostering ecosystem resilience and biodiversity protection. IoT technology will continue to advance through research and innovation, which will improve its uses in environmental monitoring contexts and for monitoring water temperature in particular. Through promoting cooperation among scientists, politicians, and communities, we may fully utilize IoT sensors to protect water resources and maintain the well-being of aquatic ecosystems for upcoming generations.

REFERRENCES

- [1] Das, Brinda, and P. C. Jain. "Real-time water quality monitoring system using Internet of Things." In *2017 International conference on computer, communications and electronics (Comptelix)*, pp. 78-82. IEEE, 2017.
- [2] Mustapha, Umar Farouk, Abdul-Wadud Alhassan, Dong-Neng Jiang, and Guang-Li Li. "Sustainable aquaculture development: a review on the roles of cloud computing, internet of things and artificial intelligence (CIA)." *Reviews in Aquaculture* 13, no. 4 (2021): 2076-2091.
- [3] Zulkifli, Che Zalina, Salem Garfan, Mohammed Talal, A. H. Alamoodi, Amneh Alamlah, Ibraheem YY Ahmaro, Suliana Sulaiman et al. "IoT-based water monitoring systems: a systematic review." *Water* 14, no. 22 (2022): 3621.
- [4] Komathy, K. "Ballast Water Quality Compliance Monitoring Using IoT." In *Information and Communication Technology for Sustainable Development: Proceedings of ICT4SD 2018*, pp. 443-451. Springer Singapore, 2020.
- [5] Glasgow, Howard B., JoAnn M. Burkholder, Robert E. Reed, Alan J. Lewitus, and Joseph E. Kleinman. "Real-time remote monitoring of water quality: a review of current applications, and advancements in sensor, telemetry, and computing technologies." *Journal of experimental marine biology and ecology* 300, no. 1-2 (2004): 409-448.
- [6] Solano, Fernando, Steffen Krause, and Christoph Wöllgens. "An internet-of-things enabled smart system for wastewater monitoring." *IEEE Access* 10 (2022): 4666-4685.
- [7] Rathna, R., U. V. Anbazhagu, L. Mary Gladence, V. Maria Anu, and J. Sybi Cynthia. "An intelligent monitoring system for water quality management using internet of things." In *2021 8th International Conference on Smart Computing and Communications (ICSCC)*, pp. 291-297. IEEE, 2021.
- [8] AlMetwally, Saif Allah H., Mohamed K. Hassan, and Mohamed H. Mourad. "Real time internet of things (IoT) based water quality management system." *Procedia CIRP* 91 (2020): 478-485.
- [9] Prapti, Dipika Roy, Abdul Rashid Mohamed Shariff, Hasfalina Che Man, Norulhuda Mohamed Ramli, Thinagaran Perumal, and Mohamed Shariff. "Internet of Things (IoT)-based aquaculture: An overview of IoT application on water quality monitoring." *Reviews in Aquaculture* 14, no. 2 (2022): 979-992.
- [10] Miasayedava, Lizaveta, Keegan McBride, and Jeffrey Andrew Tuhtan. "Automated environmental compliance monitoring of rivers with IoT and open government data." *Journal of Environmental Management* 303 (2022): 114283.